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Assessment of Educational Management Research Performance of Universities in North Eastern Nigeria

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Abstract

Nigerian universities have the capacities to perform in terms of educational management research quality and impact to promote research excellence. This will market the institutions in order to attract funding and make them more flexible, cost efficient and responsive to the need of the society. More so, the allocation of research funds to universities now depends wholly or partly on the results of assessment performance of the previous researches in educational management. This paper assessed institutional, national, external research incomes, publications and training in educational management research performance of universities in North Eastern Nigeria. The study combined a strong document analysis of the previous researches and interviews of staff in Research and Development units or centres of all universities providing research funding for educational management research in North Eastern Nigeria. Percentage was utilized for data analysis. The findings of the research show that Universities performed lowly in terms of institutional, national, external income, publications and training performance in universities of North Eastern Nigeria. The study also concluded that universities research performance in educational management is low in North Eastern Nigeria. The study further recommended among others that researchers training in educational management should be promoted through Masters and Ph. D programmes in the universities of North Eastern Nigeria.

Keywords: Assessment, Educational Management, Research Performance, Universities, North Eastern Nigeria

Introduction

Research assessment has emerged as a key science policy issue in most countries of the world (Martin & Guena, 2000.) This has been driven by the increasing demand for accountability in the context of growing constraints on public funding at a time when the number of educational management research activities going for funds is escalating. Consequently, governments have started to implement mechanisms for allocating resources that relate funding to some assessment of university research output or performance.

In the current university environment, scoring well on assessment criteria of research performance establishes authenticity as researching academics at external, institutional and national level, thereby providing capital for the purchase of increasingly scarce resources (time, money) needed for further research (Briggs, Coleman,

Morrison, 2012). Universities in Nigeria have the capacities to perform in terms of educational management research quality and impact to promote research excellence. This will market the institutions in order to attract funding and make them more flexible, cost-efficient and responsive to the needs of the society. Moreso, the allocation of research funds in universities now depends on wholly or partly on research performance of the previous researches.

Nigeria Tertiary Education Trustfund (TETFUND) is responsible for financing research apart from institutional ones by universities themselves in North Eastern Nigeria. Assessments of research performance are conducted by TETFUND at national and institutional levels. The purpose of assessing research performance is to decide how to distribute research funds to universities through some form of rankings. Different assessment of research performance mechanisms employs different criteria and methodologies depending on which aspects of performance are being assessed. Assessment tended to focus on four main aspects; external, national, institutional research income, publications, and training performance (Harris,1993).

As regards assessment methods, the literature on research performance shows that bibliometric analysis and peer review are the main approaches to assessing the quality and impact of research. However, given the time-consuming and costly character of bibliometric analysis as well as drawbacks, it is not practical for macro-level assessments such as those focusing in all the universities in North Eastern Nigeria. This leaves peer review, despite its short comings as the main assessment method for macro-level research. It is sometimes supplemented with publication and citation data and other related information, which is referred to as informed peer review. The danger of an over by simplistic application of assessment and techniques for assessing research outcomes is that data become a substitute for decision making (Like, 1992).

Assessment of research performance is for policy makers to know they are receiving value for money. But it is important to know that with respect to assessment of research performance for funding purposes, more actors are involved than just university researches and government bureaucrats. The ability to attract research funds depends upon the research focus of the institution at the University, faculty or school and whether or not these are aligned with national priorities. The ability of a university to win research funds will, therefore, depend somewhat upon its capacity to fit within national priorities or institutions (Mauch&Park,2003).

Harris (1993) argues that assessment of research performance is a concern with external, national and institutional income, publications and research training. The number and value of research grants and contracts gained are thought to be a good proxy for research performance, presumably, because one must have good research capacity to win a research grant or contract (Meek & Verder Lee 2005). Aldo and Ben (2001) stated that the value of research grants is a reflection of the quality or the department, as granting bodies give money only to establish high-quality researches to typically have excellent track records in producing important researches. As with other assessments, it is past success in research that determines current success (Rudd, 1988).

As nations increasingly have to formulate appropriate and effective policies they are turning to the development of reliable techniques for monitoring research outputs, both in relation to the production of knowledge and the use of research for economic development (Wood, 1990). Rudd (1988) further notes that there is an assumption that everyone has an equal chance of getting his (or her) result into print, however, there is evidence to suggest that this is not always the case due for example to factors relating to the author notoriety and institutions. Many of the techniques used to measure to the number of publications are based on the statistical analysis of publication rates and a citation of what is known as bibliometric. Bibliometrics is the application of mathematics and statistical methods to books and other media of communication (ASTEC, 1989). It is also the qualitative measurement of the properties of a literature usually as an aid in exploring the production, distribution and utilization of its contents (ASTEC,1989). Another indices use for assessing research performance is research training. These are researches conducted through masters by research and Ph.D. completions within time and by field of study in universities (Meek &Vander Lee, 2005).

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to assess the research performance in educational management research in universities of Northern Eastern Nigeria. Specifically, the study determined:

1. External income for educational management research performance in universities of North Eastern Nigeria.
2. National income for educational management research performance in universities of North Eastern Nigeria.
3. Institutional income for educational management research performance in universities of North Eastern Nigeria.
4. Publications from educational management research performance in universities of North Eastern Nigeria.
5. Research training in educational Management research performance in universities of North Eastern Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the external income performance for educational management research in universities of North eastern Nigerians?
2. What is the national income performance for educational management research in Universities of North Eastern Nigerians?
3. What is the institutional income performance for educational management research in universities of North Eastern Nigerian?
4. What is the publication's performance in educational management research in universities of North Eastern Nigeria?
5. What is the educational management research training performance in universities of North Eastern Nigeria?
6. What is the educational management research performance on all the indicators in Universities of North Eastern Nigerians?

Theoretical Framework and Literature Review

Assessing University – based research is a complex process. It is most often under taken to inter alia, improve research performance and quality, allocate resources, drive research mission, differentiate or promote innovation and community engagement (European Union, 2010). No simple set of indicators can meet all these requirements or provide all solutions. Each purpose requires different data. Some requirements demand extremely detailed and robust data on research outputs; other requirements demand only a few relatively simple indicators. All indicators have advantages and disadvantages, and there are limitations to all assessment exercises (Cobral & Ttuët, 2013). This study was based on a combination of indicators from research assessment procedures from United kingdom research assessment exercise (RAE), Excellence in Research of Australia (ERA) and New Zealand performance-based Research Fund (PBRF) (Besley, 2009). These consist of indicators of research performance which are used to evaluate institutional performance both within and between universities.

Hallinger(2012) presented a framework for scholars carrying out reviews that meet the international standard for publications. It draws on a database of reviews of researches previously conducted in educational leadership and management. Forty(40) reviews of researches that had been published in educational leadership were identified. The findings show high quality reviews of research which represent a powerful means of reducing the gap between research and practice. Yet the quality of research reviews conducted in educational leadership and management remains highly valuable in methodological rigor.

A research evaluation was conducted by AALTO(2009) using peer-review method in Finland. The steering committee used data collection and self evaluations of departments. This included one week site visits under taken by nine (9) international panels. The assessment was base on written assessments on grades on the basis of

the materials submitted by the departments and interviews conducted during the visits. The assessment shows that evaluation of departments had some difficulty in carrying out self-evaluation especially in answering questions regarding issues that are not usually raised in research assessments on societal impact, research environment and future potential.

A research assessment exercises were conducted by Agence d, evaluation de la recherch et de l'enseignement suprieur (AERERS) (2007) in France. Peer-review methodology was adopted. The criteria used were quality research international recognition of the laboratory in national/international networks or programmes, risk-taking in research and openness to inter-disciplinary interfaces. The result of the evaluation system is the allocation of funding to research teams by the Ministry of Higher Education and institutions using the exercise as a benchmarking exercise to improve rate by closing down sectors with poor research performance.

WSENSCHAFTSRAT(2005) conducted a research performance assessment in Germany. It was piloted based on peer review, information from departments, metrics and reviewers panel. Media rankings and league tables were distinguished by a number of characteristic like informed peer-review, discipline, specific manner from experts, level of research units and six different criteria which are not aggregated to an overall result. The result shows that only peer-review esteems for the five dimensions were published but not the indicators. The relationship between performance judged on the basis of indicators and the marks given by the peers was not transparent.

Research Council of Norway(2009) was conducted an evaluation of excellent research performance in Norway. The methodology was base on the education component and research component to restructure the Norwegian research system. Some of the result based research components were a number of doctorates, scientific publications, funding for Research Council of Norway(RCN) and funding from the EU framework programme. The results show an improvement of scientific quality within the Norwegian higher education system. It also indicated a weakness of the research component that it concerns all research areas and all institutions.

Another research assessment was also carried out by Swedish Research Council(2008) on government research bill 2008 in Sweden. The methodology was base on bibliometric indicators and external funding. The bibliometric indicator part is base on quite complex method of assessing scientific performances and comparing it between science fields, using ISI web of science, taking into account both science area adjusted publication volume and normalized citations. The external funding part on the other hand essentially includes all external funding and treating all external funding sources with equal weight. The consequence was to generate incentives and resources for universities to prioritise, manage and perform research in a way that improves the scientific quality and attractiveness of Swedish research environment in terms of external research funding, research cooperation and talented research and student inflow.

An assessment of research output of university teachers in terms of publications was conducted by Spanish Research Council(2010) in Spain. The assessment method took into consideration different fields and quality of publications measured by articles in JCR and their impact factor. In a number of fields, books in humanities or patents in engineering were also considered. Science fields were broken down into 11 fields: mathematics and physics, chemistry; cellular and molecular biology; biomedical sciences; natural sciences; engineering and architecture; social, political and educational sciences; law and jurisprudence; history and art; philosophy and linguistics. The result shows that the quantity and quality of research and publication of research results were in international journals. Several Spanish journals conscious of the importance of being included in the JCR or other national or international database, have improved the evaluation and peer-review processes. There change of behavior of a substantial number of researchers, who now orient their research activities and publication habits mainly towards JCR, the only journals that are considered worthwhile.

Colman, Dhillon, and Coulthard (1994) conducted a bibliometric evaluation of the research performance of nine(9) British universities politics departments on publications in leading journals with the highest citation impact factors. It was an analysis of articles published between1987-1992. Annual performance scores were

obtained by dividing each departmental number of publications in these journals in each year and departmental productivity by the corresponding size. These scores were summed to obtain a research performance score for each department over the period of assessment. The findings show a significant correlation with research performance scores from two previous studies using different methods.

Bazeley(2010) uses a structured survey in which academics elaborated on eight(8) different attributes of high-performing researchers to build a conceptual model of research performance. The result indicated that research performance was seen to comprise two basic components, with six(6) secondary level dimensions and a range of potential indicators. There were four(4) essential dimensions of research performance: engagement, task orientation, research practice, and intellectual processes. Two other alternative dimensions of research performance were dissemination and collegial engagement. The findings further show that research performance was seen to occur within conditions provided by an institutional context(education and training, opportunity and resources, which can bring a range of outcomes(product, impact, reputation).

Perry (2017) used bibliometric data to assess the performance of educational research in Australian universities. This study serves as an alternative perspective for excellence in research for Australia(ERA) assessment. The result indicates that Australian universities are performing above the world average in educational research. Australian universities perform especially well on the citation and peer-review process.

Geare&Edgar(2011) examined features of research managerial practice and culture within university departments. A comparative research design comprising of both interview and survey data was sourced from multiple stakeholders from Newzealand universities. The study sought to identify factors associated with supervisor research performance. The outcome of the research show that autonomy and egalitarianism along with a strong cultural ethos, supporting achievement and individualism are characteristic of high functioning departments. Management and academics in higher education settings should consider these findings of interest and benefit as universities in a number of countries approach further rounds of research performance.

Wood(1990) reported the views of academic staff on overall research performance from one Australian university on such issues like the determinants of research performance and the importance of individual autonomy in the education of research topics. The findings of the report show that research activities are highly valuable and influenced by number of factors including: personal characteristic; difference in research style, methods and strategies both within and between disciplines; and depending on funding. The study further revealed that academics firmly believe in freedom of inquiry in the choice of research topics. All the literature reviewed by discipline and countries but not on educational management research. Few of the literature was reviewed on educational leadership and management research. None was reviewed on North Eastern Nigeria, which indicates gap for the present study.

Methodology

The population of the study comprises of 550 academic and senior non-academic staff of educational management departments and research and development units or centre's of the thirteen (13) public and private universities in North Eastern Nigeria. In all the 13 universities, there was a department in which educational management is taught and researched and in the majority of cases, it is easy to identify. It is usually called a department of education, department of educational management, science education and educational foundations. All the 550 academic and senior non-academic staff in the centres or units of research and development and educational management departments participated in the study.

The data for the study was qualitatively drawn from two sources: a strong document analysis of records in research and development centres or units and education departments of the 13 universities. Interviews were also directed to academic and senior non-academic staff of research and development units and education departments. There were twenty interview items generated from the four assessment research performance variables of national, institutional, external income, publications and training. Percentage was descriptively used

to analyse the performance of research grants (external, national and institutional), publications and research training. This was utilized to determine the research performance of the universities in North Eastern Nigeria.

Results

The results were presented from the document analysis and data collected from respondents.

Research Question One: What is the external income performance for educational management research in universities of North Eastern Nigeria?

Table I: Percentage of research performance of universities in educational management on external income in North Eastern Nigeria

S/N	University	Number of External Income researches	Percentage of External Income research performance
1.	Abti American University, Yola	2000	30%
2.	Adamawa State University, Mubi	50	1%
3.	Modibbo Adama University of Technology, Yola	500	8%
4.	Taraba State University, Jalingo	100	2%
5.	Federal University, Wukari	40	1%
6.	University of Maiduguri	1200	16%
7.	Yobe State University, Damaturu	45	1%
8.	Federal University Gashua	75	0%
9.	Bauchi State University Gadau	55	0%
10.	Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi	1500	22%
11.	Gombe State University, Gombe	600	9%
12.	Federal University, Kashere	400	6%
13.	Jubilee University, Wukari	80	2%
TOTAL		6,645	100

Table1 indicates below 50% of research performance in education management on external income in universities. Abti-American and Tafawa Balewa Universities performed the highest with 30% and 22% respectively. This also shows that educational management research performance of the universities on external income was low in North Eastern Nigeria.

Research Question Two: What is national income performance for educational management research in universities of North Eastern Nigeria?

Table 2: Percentage of research performance of universities in educational management on national income in North Eastern Nigeria.

S/N	University	Number of National Income Research	Percentage of National Income Research Performance
1.	Abti American University, Yola	500	8%
2.	Adamawa State University, Mubi	30	0%
3.	Modibbo Adama University of Technology, Yola	1200	13%
4.	Taraba State University, Jalingo	50	1%
5.	Federal University, Wukari	100	10%
6.	University of Maiduguri	1500	18%
7.	Yobe State University, Damaturu	45	1%
8.	Federal University, Gashua	100	10%

9.	Bauchi State University, Gadau	60	1%
10.	Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi	1800	22%
11.	Gombe State University, Gombe	90	1%
12.	Federal University, Kashere	1100	15%
13.	Jubilee University, Wukari	30	0%
TOTAL		6,605	100

The data in table 2 above shows below fifty (50) percent of education management research performance on national income in the Universities. University of Maiduguri and Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi performed 18% and 22% respectively. This indicates that the educational management research performance on national income was low in Universities of North Eastern Nigeria.

Research Question Three: What is the institutional income performance of educational management research in universities of North Eastern Nigeria?

Table 3: Percentage of research performance of universities in educational management on institutional income in North Eastern Nigeria.

S/No	University	Number of Institutional income Researches	Percentage of Institutional Income Research performance
1	Abti American University, Yola	800	19%
2	Adamawa State University, Mubi	50	1%
3	Modibbo Adama University of Technology, Yola	450	11%
4	Taraba State University, Jalingo	200	5%
5	Federal University Wakari	400	10%
6	University of Maiduguri	700	12%
7	Yobe State University, Damaturu	55	9%
8	Federal University, Gashua	150	4%
9	Bauchi State University, Gadau	37	1%
10	Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi	950	10%
11	Gombe State University, Gombe	100	2%
12	Federal University Kashere	200	5%
13	Jubilee University, Wukari	120	3%
Total		4,212	100%

The data in the table 3 above show below fifty (50) percent educational management research performance on institutional income in the Universities. Abti -American and Tafawa Balewa universities performed with 19% and 18% respectively, as institutional income performance. This indicates that educational management research performance on institutional income was low in universities of North Eastern Nigeria.

Research Question Four: What is the publication performance of educational management research in universities of North Eastern Nigeria?

Table 4: Percentage of educational management research performance of universities on publications in North Eastern Nigeria.

S/no	University	Number of Publications from Research	Percentage of Publications from Research Performance
1	Abti American University, Yola	1000	24%
2	Adamawa State University, Mubi	100	3%
3	Modibbo Adama University of Technology, Yola	600	15%
4	Taraba State University, Jalingo	75	2%
5	Federal University, Wukari	40	1%
6	University of Maiduguri	800	20%
7	YobeState University, Damaturu	30	1%
8	Federal University Gashua	20	1%
9	Bauchi State University, Gadau	25	1%
10	Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi	750	19%
11	Gombe State University, Gombe	150	4%
12	Federal University Kashere	300	8%
13	Tubilee University, Wukari	50	1%
	Total	3,940	100%

Table 4 indicates below fifty (50) percent of educational management research performance on publications in universities of North Eastern Nigeria. Abti- American and Tafawa Balewa universities performed with 24% and 19% respectively as highest performing universities. This shows that educational management research performance on publications was low in universities of North Eastern Nigeria.

Research Question Five: What is the training performance on educational management research in universities of North Eastern Nigeria?

Table 5: Percentage of performance of universities on training in educational management research in North Eastern Nigeria?

S/No	University	Number of research trainings	Percentage of Research Training performance
1	Abti American University, Yola	200	2%
2	Adamawa State University, Mubi	400	4%
3	Modibbo Adama University of Technology, Yola	3000	29%
4	Taraba State University, Jalingo	500	5%
5	Federal University, Wukari	0	0%
6	University of Maiduguri	3500	34%
7	Yobe State University, Damaturu	0	0%
8	Federal University Gashua	0	0%
9	Bauchi State University, Gadau	0	0%
10	Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi	2500	25%
11	Gombe State University, Gombe	100	1%
12	Federal University, Kashere	0	0%
13	Jubilee University, Wukari	0	0%
	Total	10,200	100%

The data in table 5 show below 50% educational management research performance on research training in the thirteen (13) universities. Tafawa Balewa and Modibbo Adama University of Technology performed with 34%

and 29% respectively as high performing universities. This indicates that educational research performance on research training in universities of North Eastern Nigeria was low.

Research Question Six: What is the educational management research performance of universities on performance indicators in North Eastern Nigeria?

Table 6: Percentage of educational management research performance on performance indicators in universities of North Eastern Nigeria.

S/No	Performance Indicators	Number of respondents	Percentage of research performance
1	External income	100	18%
2	National income	130	24%
3	Institutional income	150	27%
4	Publications	20	4%
5	Training	150	27%
	Total	550	100%

The data in table 6 above indicated below fifty (50%) percent in educational management research performance on performance indicators in the thirteen (13) universities. Universities research performance in educational management on institutional and training performance with 27% and 27% respectively. They also performed lowly in external income and publications with 18% and 4% respectively. This shows that educational research performance on performance indicators was low in universities of North Eastern Nigeria.

Findings of the Study

The following are summaries of findings of the research:

1. The educational management research performance on external income was low with 30% and 22% as highest performing and 1% as lowest performing universities.
2. There was a low educational management research performance on national income with 22% and 8% as highest performing and 0% as lowest performing universities.
3. The 19% and 18% highest performing and 1% lowest performing universities show low educational management research performance on institutional income.
4. The educational management research performance on publications was low with 24% and 19% as highest performing and 1% as low performing universities.
5. There was a low educational management research management performance on research training with 34% and 29% as highest performing and 0% as lowest performing universities in North Eastern Nigeria.
6. The 27% and 27% highest performing and 18% and 4% as lowest performing universities show low educational management research performance on performance indicators in North Eastern Nigeria

Discussion

Table 1 shows that the educational management research performance of universities on external income was low in North Eastern Nigeria. The performance of all universities was below fifty (50%) percent. Two thousand (2000) documents representing thirty (30%) percent from Abti American University, Yola and one thousand five hundred (1500) documents representing twenty two (22%) were the highest performing universities with the lowest performing ones having one percent (1%) each performance on external income. The data in the table 2 shows that educational management research performance on national income was low in North Eastern Nigeria. The performance of all the universities was below fifty (50%). One thousand eight hundred (1800) (22%) documents from Tafawa Balewa University and one thousand five hundred (1500) documents representing eighteen (18%) percent from University of Maiduguri were the most performing on national income. They were lowest performing universities with one percent (1%) on National income. The educational management research performance on national income was low. Table 3 indicate that the educational management research

performance of universities was below fifty (50%) percent. Abti American University, Yola had eight hundred(800) documents representing nineteen percent (19%) and Tafawa Balawa University having nine hundred and fifty (950) representing eighteen (18%) percent were the highest performing universities with the lowest performing one's Adamawa State University, Mubi and Bauchi State University, Gadau, having one (1%) percent each on institutional income.

The finding in table 4 shows that educational management research performance of universities on publication was low. Abti American University with one thousand (1000) documents representing twenty four (24%) percent and University of Maiduguri having eight hundred(800) documents representing nineteen (19%) percent were also the highest performing. Universities with the lowest performing ones are Federal University, Wukari, Yobe State University, Damaturu Federal University, Gashua, Bauchi State University, Gadau and Jubilee University, Wukari having one percent (1%) research performance on institutional income.

The findings in table 5 indicate that the educational management research performance of universities on research training was low. The performance of all the thirteen universities was below fifty (50%) percent. Modibbo Adama university of Technology, Yola which had three thousand (3000) documents representing twenty nine percent (29%) and University of Maiduguri having three thousand, five hundred (3500) documents representing thirty four (34%) percent were the highest performing universities with the lowest-performing ones as Yobe State University, Damaturu, Federal University, Gashua, Bauchi State University, Gadau, Federal University Kashere and Jubilee University Wukari having zero (0%) percent in terms of research training performance.

The finding in table 6 shows that the educational management research performance of the universities on the five performance indicators was low. The performance of all the thirteen universities on the indicators was below fifty (50%) percent. Out of the five performance indicators, the universities highly performed on institutional income with 150 respondents representing 27% and research training with 150 respondents representing twenty-seven (27%) percent. The lowest research performance was on publications, external income and national income with twenty (20) responses, representing four (4%) percent, one hundred (100) respondents representing eighteen (18%) percent and one hundred and thirty (130) respondents representing twenty four (24%) percent on the performance indicators.

Conclusion

The overall evidence from the study shows that the performance in educational management research of universities was generally low in North Eastern Nigeria. Universities conducting educational management research need to boost research outputs in order to attract funding for research. They also need to disseminate findings through publications in high ranking journals and train researchers through post-graduate programs in educational management.

Recommendations

The following recommendations came out of the findings of the study:

1. All educational management researches should have quality and impact to attract external income for research in the Universities of North Eastern Nigeria.
2. Universities should insist on implementation of educational management research findings and recommendations to attract national income for universities in North Eastern Nigeria.
3. Universities should attract institutional income from internally generated revenue and consultancy services.
4. Research findings should be disseminated through publications in high ranking Journals.
5. The training of researchers should be promoted through Masters and Ph.D programs of universities.
6. Universities should boost research outputs to attract funding to serve the needs of the society

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